

Automated Data-Ops for Community-Driven Flood Monitoring

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Summary

Communities from deprived urban areas suffer from socio-environmental challenges and data scarcity to tackle them. Geoinformation and cloud computing can support monitoring, analysing, and data-driven decision making while helping authorities and communities co-design and co-produce data. Automation through DataOps might facilitate the development and operation of heterogeneous data flows. However, its implementation implies a steep learning curve and requirements difficult to meet. This paper describes a vision to adopt DataOps in citizen-generated data production, improve data flows and integrate heterogeneous data sets. We discuss the challenges and efforts of setting data pipelines for a community-driven monitoring network in Brazil.

KEYWORDS: Data Flows, Data Pipelines, DataOps, Flooding, Citizen-generated

1. Introduction

Geoinformation and cloud computing increasingly support achieving and monitoring sustainable development goals SDGs (Wu et al., 2020). While communities from deprived urban areas face socio-environmental challenges, the information needed to understand and make decisions is usually scarce (de Sherbinin et al., 2021). Adding a geographic component empowers communities to complement existing monitoring networks with co-produced data (Kocaman et al., 2021; Porto de Albuquerque et al., 2019). Various citizen and community-oriented initiatives have contributed to scientific and social development worldwide (Klonner et al., 2016). At the same time, big data industries have adopted DataOps and various technologies (e.g., cloud, serverless, on-premises) to automate data flows and pipelines (e.g., structured, semistructured, non-structured) (Munappy et al., 2020). However, community-led strategies have not adopted the same approach extensively despite their potential benefits.

The idea of using cloud technologies and DevOps to ease data management and operation is attractive for data collection, access and publication projects (Munappy et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020). Nevertheless, community-led initiatives usually lack technology expertise for making it and usually focus more on functional agreements rather than on software deployment. Additionally, standard functionalities in citizen-generated data strategies such as programming interfaces and data storage solutions are usually supported by server-oriented architectures and relational databases. On the other hand, novel services such as non-SQL databases, data lakes and processing functions only become viable alternatives after ensuring the specialised knowledge needed (Yang et al., 2017). Moreover, although cloud providers claim they provide user-friendly interfaces, community members might find it hard to use.

The team designed a platform to support the Waterproofing Data project based on the underlying research question: how can a DataOps approach benefit community-led and co-production data strategies?. The project investigates the governance of water-related risks, focusing on social and cultural aspects of data practices. Data flows, co-production, and the data practices involved will support a transcultural dialogue with government organisations and local administration involved in flood risk management. In particular, the project aims at generating data at the local level by engaging

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citizens and integrating citizen-generated data and other sources using geo-computational techniques. The long-term impact of this project is a contribution towards the SDG 11 Sustainable Cities and communities and targets 11.5 and 11.B.

The paper uses a case study to analyse the challenges and efforts of setting data pipelines for a community-driven monitoring network in five states of Brazil. The following sections describe the identified data flows, the proposed architecture to manage data pipelines and flows, and the results. It ends with a discussion of how the adoption of DataOps might benefit monitoring flooding in the Waterproofing Data project and, in general, citizen-generated data production.

2. Data and methods

The case study triggered two main actions to implement DataOps. First, an evaluation of the data flows, data sources, interfaces and storage schemas involved in co-producing flood-related data in Brazil (e.g., rainfall measures, susceptibility areas, rain, floods). Second, an evaluation of potential cloud services to define the architecture. The analysis considered the communities involved in data collection (e.g., mobile app and web portal) and official data producers (e.g., CEMADEN and CPRM) as endpoints together with the need to decouple components. These considerations should ensure platform evolution, migration and integration of additional data sources, either citizen-generated or authoritative.

2.1. Data flows

The design considered flows in which citizens and authorities in Brazil can improve flood monitoring networks. From the citizen perspective, flows were the registration of self-made pluviometers used to report daily rainfall measures, also descriptive observations of rain and flooding events. From the authorities perspective, the flows involved official rainfall measures, areas susceptible to flooding and weather forecasts. In a second stage, the team defined how frequently the data flows were triggered and how critical the updates were to classify them into hot and cold (see **Table 1**). Finally, the design considered integration and comparison data flows.

Table 1 Data flows and roles identified by the Waterproofing Data project

Stakeholder and Role	Flow	Description
Citizens as data producers and consumers	Pluviometer registration (cold)	Citizens report the location and description of self-made pluviometers for their rainfall measures.
	Rainfall Measure (hot)	Citizens with self-made pluviometers report rainfall measures daily. They can view and amend updated values.
	Rain Event (Hot)	A citizen report rain or flooding events. The report includes the location, a short description and images.
	Flooding Event (Hot)	
CEMADEN as data producer	Official Rainfall measure (hot)	Authorities with monitoring networks provide rainfall measures. Official networks will be complemented with citizen-generated data.
CPRM as data producer	Flooding areas (cold)	A hydrogeological study provides areas susceptible to flooding. These areas frame citizen-generated reports, and future exercises would provide updates
CEMADEN and private forecast providers	Weather forecast (Cold)	Short-term weather forecasts from official and private providers would notify citizens through the mobile application.

Since the design must consider future changes in data structures, flows, and user requirements, adding an automated operation through DataOps addressed these requirements. Therefore, the researchers

added considerations for data pipelines handling these changes and a definition for smart or resilient data flows (Rawat and Narain, 2019). The case study showed that changes in data flows might usually come from modified data structures, new data sources, inconsistent data or deprecated access links.

To address these needs, the team adopted two criteria. The first was adopting flexible data formats for citizen and official data sources. For example, we adopted JSON across the platform, and ingestion handled potential inputs not offering the right information. The second criterion was using non-SQL storage for ingested through a data lake. A data lake ensures the storage of structured, semistructured and unstructured data for current and future data flows and pipelines.

2.2. DataOps Architecture

Based on the identified data flows and design criteria, the design started from the clients interacting with flood-related data and their functional requirements. As endpoints, the design considered clients (e.g., mobile and web applications) and authoritative sources (e.g., CEMADEN, CPRM and other official providers). Thus, the back-end component needed to, on the one hand, ensure citizens can contribute their data to the platform and, on the other hand, enable data storage and access to citizens and authorities contributing to the platform.

The initial architecture focused on the back-end components from two types: storage and interfaces, as shown in **Figure 1**. Storage components combine a relational database schema that executes pre-defined queries from clients and non-SQL storage that handles temporary ingested data and permanent records data despite their correctness. Interfaces handle ingestion and query requests from citizens and authorities.

Ingestion relies on a server-less service handling data pipelines dynamic loads. Python-based Azure functions enabled the ingestion API. The functions store the ingested JSON files in the data lake, then process and save data in the PostgreSQL database.

Data query relies on a traditional relational schema and a Node.js server operating dynamic queries for mobile and web clients. The Node.js API handles connection and data extraction from PostgreSQL and deliver results to authenticated clients. Although this approach cannot scale based on demand, it speeds up the development to fit the project's schedule.

Figure 1 WPD hybrid architecture proposed.

3. Results

Results from the case study comprise the deployed cloud platform to process hot and cold data flows through a hybrid storage schema (i.e., a data lake complemented with a relational database) and the flood data produced by communities in Brazil. The mobile application "Dados a prova d'agua" (i.e., Translation of Waterproofing data into Portuguese) allowed more than 370 citizens to collect flood-related data and therefore use the cloud platform to provide more than 5.710 measures from November 1 2021 to January 15 2022. On average, the platform recorded 22 reports per user across the states of São Paulo, Pernambuco, Mato in Brazil, Santa Catarina and Acre. **Figure 2** shows measures and the spatial distribution during the testing period.

Figure 2 Map of citizens' submissions to the Waterproofing Data project.

4. Discussion and Findings

The test phase showed how a cloud platform could adopt DevOps to support flood-related data production. However, the scientific contribution exceeds the platform and covers the proof of concept for automating data pipelines and components deployment. Implementing DevOps for citizen science stands as a novel contribution that implies a critical review of data flows and the potential evolution of data integration within community-led projects. The proposed architecture tackles issues such as configuring pipelines and the integration of official and citizen-generated data sets.

Although our case study produced positive results, further monitoring and adjustment are still needed during the operation. Full benefits from DevOps and DataOps would come only after integrating new data flows and validating how these flows adapt to multiple disruptions on the fly (both hot and cold). Additionally, version control (i.e. GitHub integration), operation monitoring, and notification schemas still need the implementation to benefit developers and platform managers. However, to-be-developed

features should not hide the benefits of speeding up the development and deployment of the Waterproofing platform. Instead, they become the foundations for future citizen-driven initiatives considering cloud services for handling heterogeneous data and faster deployment.

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Biographies

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